

FEATURES OF THE ENGLISH JOKE

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Shomuratov Gayrat Shomurot ugli

*Master's student of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Uzbekistan.*

Abstract: *The article deals with some general information of English humor, the place of the English jokes in humorous literary traditions, about the unique authors' style of some of the most celebrity writers, about verbal and non-verbal and such kind of methods and peculiarities of creating a comic effect.*

Keywords: *English humour, the main concepts of humour, characteristic of humor, English jokes, the piggy bank of English humor.*

As you know, the word humor comes from the Latin humor (liquid) and came into the Russian language through English, in which humor originally meant character, mood.

In the modern sense, humor is a kind of comic, which has a world-contemplative character and a complex tone in assessing life, where the serious is hidden under the mask of the funny. The fantasy of humor reveals, according to N.V. Gogol, "tears invisible to the world" - for insignificant great, for insanity wisdom, for funny sad. In the parable of humor, it is said that joy and sorrow met in the forest; not recognizing each other, they entered into a marriage union, from which humor was born.

The concept of "humor" is ambiguous. In a broad sense, humor is defined as a good-natured, mocking attitude towards individual phenomena of life and towards the world as a whole. In a narrower sense, it is a method of self-expression of a creative personality, on the basis of which works of comic genres are created. Among them, tall and comic forms are distinguished. The former includes works of fiction and art, the latter include parodies, jokes, anecdotes, tales, jokes, ditties, cartoons, friendly cartoons[2,300].

The national flavor is also characteristic of humor. So, English humor is considered to be subtle and aristocratic. It is distinguished by exaggerated calmness and elegance. Researchers believe that English humor is based on the centuries-old habit of the British to suppress the external expression of their emotions. The British have a special knack for saying funny things with imperturbable seriousness. This special gift of the nation is evidenced by the works of the classics of English fiction: Shakespeare, Byron, Thackeray, Oscar Wilde, Jerome K. Jerome, Aldous

Huxley and the Hungarian George Mikish, beloved by all Englishmen, recognized as an English writer not by birth, but by spirit

Researchers of the English character agree that humor is a national trait of the British. For them, joking is as natural as breathing. The famous Czech writer Karel Čapek noted that "the British are incredibly serious, respectable and respectable, but suddenly something flashes out, they say something very funny, sparkling with humor, and immediately become solid again, like an old leather chair." They willingly laugh at themselves and at others. This property has been cultivated in England for centuries, being considered the most important human dignity. The writers of old English books on good manners insist that a sense of humor can and should be cultivated; a person without a sense of humor is far from perfect[1,80].

Humor haunts the Englishman everywhere: in television and radio broadcasts, in books, in periodicals and in everyday life. It is no longer felt as strongly by native English speakers as by foreigners, because it is their own way of thinking. Probably no other country knows how to laugh at themselves as in England. There are no barriers to humor here, the British laugh at everything that can cause a smile, including those that have been considered sacred from time immemorial: over the powerful, over the government and even over members of the royal family.

English jokes can be "kind" or "evil." A "kind" joke cheers up both yourself and those around you. For example: On the London Underground, during a heavy downpour, passengers are told: Temple Station is closed because of unprecedented behavior of the passengers. They refused to leave the station because of the rain. (Temple Station is closed due to unprecedented passenger behavior - they refused to leave the subway due to rain).

The "evil" joke laughs at the misfortune of others. For example: There are some Ken Bigley Christmas crackers available. They're the same as normal Christmas crackers except you don't get a hat. There are Ken Bigley Christmas crackers on sale. These are regular crackers, only without hats.

Ken Bigley was an Englishman who worked in Iran, was taken hostage in 2004, tried to escape from captivity, was caught and beheaded. This is due to the lack of hats on the crackers. Many English jokes are grouped together based on the commonality of the phenomena that create the comic effect. So, in the piggy bank of English humor there are:

Ethnic slurs - ethnic jokes that play on the peculiarities of national characters in an exaggerated manner. For example: An American walking through the streets of London, passed under Canary Wharf (London's biggest building). As he stood there looking up, a lad joined him. After a while the American turned to the kid and said, "Do you realize, son, that we

have buildings like that in the States, only they're three times the size? ". " I'm not surprised, "said the kid. "That's a Lunatic Asylum! "(An American tourist, strolling through the streets of London, stops near the largest building in the city of Canary Wharf. While he is examining it, looking upwards, a young man comes up to him. The American turns to him and says:" Imagine, son, we have there are similar buildings, only three times larger. "No wonder, the boy replies, "this is a psychiatric clinic"[4,109].

Dry humor - ironic jokes in which mockery is hidden under the guise of seriousness. For example, a student asks the professor to let her go from a lecture, to which he seriously replies: I am sure it'll break my heart, but you may leave. (I'm sure it will break my heart, but you can go).

Banana-skin humor - primitive jokes. The name banana-skin humor appeared in English in 1913, when a musical was staged on the stage of one of the UK theaters, which included the following episode: a man walks down the street, almost hits a lamppost, winks knowingly at the audience, and suddenly slips onto banana peel and falls on its back. In the general context of the comedy, this episode was perceived in the audience as very funny. Since then, jokes of this kind have become known as banana jokes. For example: Why was the broom late for breakfast? - Because he swept in or: Why is the letter T like an island? - Because it's in the middle of water. (Why does the letter T look like an island? - Because it is in the middle of the water)[5,55].

Elephant jokes - stupid or flat jokes (elephant fantasies). For example, an entertainer at a concert in a seaside town addresses the audience when he sees a lady in a striped suit who is late: "Here you are, a walking deckchair". (Admire, here's a walking chaise longue). The name of this category of jokes contains the word elephant. Fashion on the theme of elephants appeared in the English-speaking environment in the sixties of the last century. The first jokes were invented by schoolchildren. In them, the elephant was presented as something large and conspicuous, but, despite its impressive dimensions, it could be recognized only by indirect signs. For example: How can you tell that the elephant is in the bathtub with you? - By the smell of peanuts on its breath. (How can you guess that there is an elephant in the bathroom with you? - By the smell of peanuts in his breath.) or: How can you tell there are two elephants in your refrigerator? - You can hear giggling when the light goes out. (How can you guess that there are not one, but two elephants in your refrigerator? - Because they giggle when the lights go out).

More often than not, jokes are created spontaneously. Some people come up with them, having inherent in themselves the ability from birth. According to Goethe, "humor is one of the elements of genius". Joke makers sense the convergence of the threads of the comic, giving a

humorous effect. The comic in an English joke can be based on irony, paradox, absurdity, repetition, reduction to the point of absurdity, hint, pseudo-contrast, reverse comparison, false amplification, exaggeration, play on words[3,16].

Irony is a category that characterizes the discrepancy between intention and result. For example, an English teacher writes the following words on the board: "woman without her man is nothing" and asks students to correctly place punctuation marks. A young student does it like this: "Woman, without her man, is nothing." (A woman is nothing without her man.) A student girl puts a different meaning in the arrangement of punctuation marks: "Woman! Without her, man is nothing. " (A woman! Without her, a man is nothing.)

The paradox is a surprise, an inadequate reaction to a statement. Instead of the expected response, the interlocutor hears something absurd, which radically changes the situation, causing laughter. For example: Sir, did you have a good holiday? - Yes! I went to France, to Paris. - Did you have much trouble with your French when you were there? - No, I didn't but the Parisians did. (Did you have a good vacation? - Yes, I was in France, in Paris. - Did you have a lot of problems with French? - No, but the Parisians did.)

Repetition is a technique for creating a comic effect by repeating words or statements. For example: Golfer: Absolutely shocking! I've never played so badly before! Caddie: Oh! Have you played before? (Golfer: Horror! I've never played so badly. Cady: Have you ever played before?) [7,109].

Hint - the creation of a comic effect by allowing the interlocutor to think independently of the essence of what happened. For example: Mother: I sent my little boy for two pounds of plums and you sent a pound and a half. Grocer: My scales are all right, madam. Have you weighed your little boy? (Mother: I sent my baby to you for two pounds of plums, and you gave him only a pound and a half. Salesman: My scales are in order, madam. Have you weighed your baby?)

Pseudo-contrast is the creation of a comic effect with the help of a statement that, at first glance, contradicts the thoughts of the interlocutor, but, in fact, enhances it. For example: Why didn't you answer the letter I sent you? - But I didn't get any letter from you. And besides I didn't like what you said in it. (Why didn't you answer my letter? - But I didn't receive any letter from you, and besides, I didn't like what you wrote in it[8,139].

A reverse comparison is the creation of a comic effect by using an expression in its direct meaning, while it is usually used in a figurative sense. For example: Suitor: I am seeking your daughter's hand. Do you have any objections? Father: None at all. Take the one that's always in my

pocket. (Suitor: I ask your daughter's hand. Do you have any objections? - Father: None, take the hand that is in my pocket all the time.)

False reinforcement - creating a comic effect by using a phrase in which, at first glance, agreement with the interlocutor's thought is expressed, but, in fact,

contains a refutation. For example: She: Jack, I am sorry to have treated you the way I did. You'll forgive me for being so mean to you last week, won't you? He: Sure! That's all right. I saved £ 25 while we weren't on speaking terms. (She: Jack, will you forgive me for being was so heartless towards you last week? He: Of course, everything is in order. I saved £ 25 while we were not talking.)

Hyperbolization - the creation of a comic effect based on the amplification of meaning. For example: How do I get to Bush House? - Turn left, at least in the morning it was there. (How do I get to Bush House? - Turn left, at least the building was there in the morning.) The building, which is called Bush House, is widely known not only in Great Britain, but all over the world. It is there that the holy of holies of the British television and radio broadcasting corporation BBC is located. The reinforcing phrase at least applied to the location of such a famous object, in this case, brings a smile[6,89].

A play on words based on ambiguity is a way of constructing a joke, creating a comic effect by using different meanings of the word, which leads to a lack of mutual understanding between the interlocutors. For example: How are they biting today? - On the neck and legs mostly. The salt of the joke is that the verb bite has two meanings - to bite (about insects and animals) and to peck (about fish). The first interlocutor is interested in how the fish bite, the second misunderstands him and tells exactly where the insects bite him.

A word play based on homonymy - creating a comic effect due to the semantic difference of homonyms. For example: Waiter! - Yes, sir. - What's this? - It's bean soup, sir. - No matter what it's been. What is it now? (Waiter! - Yes, sir. - What is it? - It's bean soup. - I don't care what it was. What is it now?)

In this joke, the lack of understanding between the interlocutors, causing a smile, is based on the difference in the meanings of homophonic words: the noun bean (beans) and the passive participle from the verb to be (to be) - been.

The ability to joke is a wonderful trait of the English. Life - affirming humor helps them in solving difficult problems, preventing aggression and conflict, relieving stress and much more. It promotes a positive attitude towards the world and says that, despite all the difficulties of what is happening, a person was, is and will be.

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